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Factors Affecting the Development of Vietnam Lacquer Paints

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Abstract:

The goal of the study is to identify the characteristics and quintessence of Vietnamese lacquer art, highlight the characteristics and quintessence, and see the difference with foreign lacquer paintings. On the basis of understanding the origin, materials, techniques, art, development, achievements ... to find out the characteristics and artistic essence of Vietnam's unique painting form - Lacquer painting (limited to fine art and visual paintings). On the basis of researching the development of materials, the exploration and experimentation of artisans and artists, understanding Vietnamese lacquer paintings in the current cultural context: exchange, integration, culture contributes to the sustainable development of Culture - Society (in which is also the potential of Tourism). The article has highlighted the role of Vietnamese lacquer paintings in honoring Vietnamese art and Vietnamese culture; contributing to the enrichment of regional and world culture. Finally, the article has emerged that the development of Vietnamese lacquer paintings is not only a matter of developing and preserving works but also a problem related to crafts, craft villages, artisans making materials, training of craftsmen and artists

Keywords: Lacquer Painting, Vietnam

1. Introduction

Vietnamese lacquer art for nearly a century has accompanied enthusiastic artists who are always exploring and researching to enrich the beauty and great potential of this unique visual material. From a traditional decorative material, they have contributed to transforming into an artistic material. That tradition is even richer through the skillful and loving hands of artists of many generations who have learned to absorb the artistic quintessence of the world and the nation to enrich the language of Vietnamese lacquer art. Today, Vietnamese art is proud to have lacquer art and that art is known to the world. It can be affirmed that since its inception, Vietnamese lacquer paintings have become more and more famous and popular. Many works in the twentieth century have become masterpieces, national treasures. Vietnamese lacquer paintings are hunted, sought after by international friends ..., becoming an expensive genre in the regional painting market.

When it comes to fine arts, Vietnamese painting, we are proud of lacquer paintings. It must be affirmed that Vietnamese lacquer paintings created by Vietnamese people on the basis of traditional national art combined with Eastern-Western visual theory have become a typical artistic value of Vietnam, giving Vietnamese art a new shade, modern identity and advanced. Vietnamese lacquer art has had a very proud development in both the field of shaping and decorating handicrafts. Vietnamese lacquer paintings with a unique and precious expression art language are the pride of the art world, creating Vietnamese cultural identity, contributing to the richness and novelty of the world's visual arts.

Studying the current state of Vietnamese lacquer paintings on the one hand helps us see the valuable values and qualities of unique paintings made by the talents of Vietnamese artists. Showing the intelligence and creative ability of Vietnamese artisans and painters, they have made miracles, creating priceless artworks imbued with national identity. Besides, we find the existence and shortcomings in the process of making vietnamese lacquer artworks today such as the issue of vocational conservation, craft villages, vocational training, honoring artisans, artists, conservation issues to preserve works. Vietnam's climate is tropical and hot and humid, so measures must be taken against warping, warping and cracking. Create a cultural environment, market for works, expensive materials, elaborate paintings, what is the price of works? The State's policy regime to help Vietnam Lacquer Painting develop. On the basis of finding development directions, affirming the value of Vietnamese lacquer paintings, affirming the importance of preserving and promoting raw materials and measures to honor crafts, craft villages, artisans and artists through focusing on policies, training, reserve traditional technologies not to be lost.

2. Research methodology

The author proceeds to combine, collect and gather resources talking about Vietnamese and foreign lacquer. At the same time, virtual observers conduct actual investigations, fieldwork, interviews, exchange of information ... with painters with high professions in lacquer, artisans, craftsmen in craft villages, production facilities, fine arts schools (lacquer department). Statistical collection of data, mapping, to create a generalization of the topic; make diagrams for comparison and comparison. Describe and analyze art, use techniques for analysis, chemical properties, physics, use synthetic methods. In addition, the author also uses the following research methods: Comparative analysis method, comparison: Analysis and evaluation of resources on information channels, comparing in practice to draw scientific conclusions between theory and practice. Applying science and technology: chemical, physical, environmental analysis methods... how it affects the creation and preservation of Vietnamese lacquer artworks (conditions for museums, private collectors...). Interdisciplinary methods: specific history, fine arts, culture, sociology, science and technology, modern technology... Use camera equipment, cameras, recorders to survey, investigate, field. Use information technology to download documents, communicate and store information and documents.

3. Current situation of Vietnam Lacquer Painting

On the basis of assessing the situation, we see that Vietnam has a precious "treasure" of lacquer paintings. The proposed comments in the development direction mention the preservation and development of traditional professions, which contributes to the development of culture and tourism. Introducing products that make a mark for Vietnamese lacquer paint, Vietnamese lacquer paintings on the market, contributing to exports (raw materials, products). Affirming that Vietnam Lacquer Painting is a Cultural Heritage contributing to the national cultural identity of Vietnam - Promoting and building an advanced culture imbued with national identity.

Organizing exhibitions helps the introduction to the public, contributing to improving the spiritual life of the people, widely promoting works and authors to the public. Strengthening international cooperation, foreign exchanges, collecting foreign currency.

The history of the development of Vietnamese lacquer paintings

Within the scope of space, time to study and place lacquer paintings (including visual paintings and fine art paintings) in relation to Vietnamese paintings and fine arts; between the present and the past, with the future we can relatively divide the stages of lacquer painting in particular, painting (us) in general. On the basis of stating the authors, works of each period at historical sites, some international domestic exhibitions, at the Museum of Fine Arts, etc., we can visualize the general appearance, see the situation and development of Vietnamese lacquer paintings.

Lacquer handicrafts, lacquer paintings

Referring to lacquer paintings, we have expanded to mention lacquer handicrafts because for painting in craft villages, craft wards, production facilities, cooperatives, handicraft companies, lacquer paintings only account for a part, about 1/3 of the previous products of Vietnamese handicraft products, lacquer is present at fine art exhibitions (TLMTTQ from 1976 onwards all have fine art works such as trays, boxes, screens, etc.). Thus, the works of applied art and visual art of the joint exhibition were later separated.

It must also be added that in the past we only had the profession of painting we made household appliances, handicrafts, painted statues, worship items, decorated pagodas, mausoleums, palaces but mainly lipstick, gold, silver coated with jewels, we had paintings but oil paint, etc. From the day the students of Indochina College of Fine Arts explored and created lacquer painting skills, the field of handicrafts has more skills in lacquer making, new lacquer handicrafts mainly make decorative paintings, vases, trays, cups, decorative plates, lacquer boxes, screens, etc. fine lacquer paintings are the strength of this field, the paintings are mass-produced, many of them show exquisite virtuosity techniques that show the exquisite beauty, ingenuity, and skill of painting of artisans.

From the day peace was restored (1954) along with the bloom and sublimation of lacquer art, lacquer art also entered a new stage with strong development. Thousands of lacquer handicraft production facilities attract millions of workers and artisans and skilled craftsmen. The factors that help this development, can be generalized as follows: an objective reason must be mentioned that the State has trade relations with countries by Protocol, mainly with socialist countries. Our largest market at that time was the Soviet Union (former) and Eastern European countries such as Poland, Romania, the German Democratic Republic and some other countries such as France, Italy, Canada ...

Our lacquer handicrafts already have a reputation in the international market, to get that result due to the centralized economic mechanism of subsidizing bureaucracy, of course, does not exclude the weaknesses of this mechanism but must affirm the positivity of the mechanism at this period.

At that time, the State encouraged the development of all handicrafts for export for foreign currency. The Central Commune Union coordinates with the Ministry of Education and Training so that establishments and localities send people to formal and in-service education at art and vocational schools to serve as technical and fine arts cores for establishments, from the central to the provinces to open vocational schools. Handicraft Import and Export Corporation cooperates with the Vietnam Fine Arts Association, with the School of Industrial Fine Arts, to compose samples for export. Artexport Corporation (which was the exclusive owner of output at that time) since 1965 has established a factory specializing in composing samples in general, mainly

lacquer goods in particular, including lacquer paintings. The state assigns the next year's plan is always higher than the previous year, producers do not have to worry about capital.

The method of production of export goods at that time was that the State sold raw materials for the purchase of finished products. All quality and price issues have been calculated correctly by the State Price Committee and the price room right in the Corporation, sufficient input to each code to the border gate. The material department is responsible for importing materials and materials for timely allocation of the right types. The technical department calculates all necessary needs for materials, processes, production stages so that the products to users are of good quality, without complaints. In order to avoid the situation of eating less raw materials, reducing the production process, localities and establishments do not allow individuals and forms of centralized work into production teams, production teams, cooperatives with daily supervision. The Corporation also sends technical and professional staff to inspect each stage of production until the finished product. Thanks to the awareness of the importance of this economic sector and the great potential for material talents, the State has adopted many specific policies and measures to improve the value of lacquer for export, including lacquer paintings in particular, cottage goods in general. The mode of production is: The State sells raw materials, buys finished products, the State holds a monopoly on materials, raw materials and consumption of goods, producers do not have to worry about output for fine arts products. The state also has policies to encourage people to grow paint, harvest paint such as providing flashlights, raincoats, boots to exploit paint at night (back then these items had to be distributed, not sold freely). The average subsidy period is distributed to buy 13 to 15kg of rice at the trade price per month, while 1kg of paint is exchanged for 3 to 5 kg of rice (depending on the quality of the paint). Satisfactory policies with growers have created conditions for the plant to grow. Many lacquer production facilities were born, attracting a large number of workers, many provinces and cities competed to develop lacquer production. In addition to the North: in Hanoi, there are 3 large establishments: Thong Nhat Cooperative, Hong Ha Cooperative, Thang Long Cooperative. Ha Son Binh province (former) has more than 20 cooperatives such as: Binh Minh has up to 500 workers, the whole province has over 2000 workers. Hebei (former) has 3 large cooperatives: Dinh Bang, Tan Hong, Phu Luu, a total of over 1000 employees. Hai Phong has Bac Son and Vinh Bao cooperatives with more than 1000 employees. Thai Binh has Vu Thu Cooperative. Thanh Hoa has Thang Loi Cooperative, War Invalids Handicraft Company with over 500 employees. Vinh Phu (former) has a large lacquer cooperative that attracts thousands of workers, etc. The South has large lacquer facilities such as Thanh Le, Song Be, Thien My, Lam Son ...

The most important thing is that the quality of the product has determined the survival of lacquer handicrafts including lacquer paintings for export. In order to ensure both technical and artistic quality, Artexport Corporation has its own factory specializing in drawing samples and regularly sends staff to the facility to check the quality. The pinnacle of this industry was marked by the 1987 National Handicraft Production and Exhibition Conference organized by the Ministry of Culture (Department of Fine Arts) in collaboration with the Central Socialist Union in Hanoi. At this Conference and Exhibition, lacquer exports including lacquer paintings were highly appreciated because this industry has helped our country earn millions of rubles - dollars, accounting for most of the export turnover of the entire foreign trade industry.

In this period, not only the foreign trade industry played an important role to bring the lacquer art industry, lacquer painting in particular and our painting industry in general to great development, but many other ministries and branches also had very close coordination. The Ministry of Culture has a fine art workshop, gathering a large number of good artists, artisans and craftsmen to promote production, improve quality, regularly add new products of lacquer and lacquer paintings. There is a new drawing room, contributing to the creation of high-quality lacquer works and products, saving a good reputation until today.

The University of Industrial Fine Arts is an important training place, the Faculty of Lacquer has provided society with thousands of talented artists and artisans mastering lacquer skills and materials.

The Central Commune Union has an institute specializing in research on handicrafts in general and lacquer art (including lacquer paintings) in particular. Also creating many new models and new products of lacquer art, the Union of Communes always has activities to encourage production facilities, traditional craft villages, regularly organizes large national exhibitions on handicrafts. The Central Commune Union also has many forms to encourage the honor of skilled artisans and craftsmen, such as working with the Ministry of Culture (Department of Fine Arts) to study the title of "Golden Hand" for those who excel in this field. Has created conditions for the "Golden Hands" to compete for talents, participate in many international exhibitions on handicrafts, in socialist countries such as the GDR, Mongolia, the Soviet Union (former). Many works and products have won worthy awards in these contests and exhibitions.

The Fine Arts Department of the Ministry of Culture at that time also had its own room "Art of Life" (in the 70s and 80s TK XX) to take care of and detect talented artisans, motivate and create conditions for them in composition and exhibition. Localities also established vocational training schools, short-term refresher classes to improve the quality of handicraft products, including lacquer paintings, typically the Handicraft School of Ha Son Binh - Ha Tay (former) in Ha Dong town, now Hanoi General Vocational Secondary School.

In summary, the 60s, 70s, 80s of the twentieth century, along with the brilliant development of lacquer art, lacquer painting, the field of lacquer art and lacquer painting is also a period of unprecedented brilliant development. In this period, there were high-quality lacquer products and paintings, worthy of being the pride of the "Golden Hands" of Vietnam. Being interested in using by the State, ministries and agencies coordinate smoothly, closely, appreciate and honor good artisans and workers and especially always be loyal to the production process, technical stages, traditional technical methods, follow the traditional skills of the paint craft, so they can cause prestige, the respect of users in many countries around the world, while also creating jobs for millions of people who have traditionally worked hard and skillfully.

An event that seems to be "Innocuous" but has a profound impact on traditional lacquer materials of Vietnam, it creates as a worrying "turning point" in our painting and handicraft process. In the years 1972-1975, at a time when our country's economy was extremely difficult, the resistance war against the US to save the country was fierce, Japanese chemical paint companies approached the Vietnamese market. They sent experts to directly guide the use of their products, and Japanese industrial paints were quickly used, spreading widely. Pô - li - sai paints, which are both much cheaper than our paint, are extremely convenient to use. It is this "superiority" that Japanese paint materials have quickly dominated the market. Artists, artisans, handicraft production establishments (including those managed by the State) raced to switch to Japanese paint, this event not only caused the techniques and materials to make traditional lacquer and optical paints of Vietnam to be shaken but also adversely affected the areas where paint materials could not be sold, so people collected. narrowing the area and diverting production.

In the period when our country switched to a market mechanism, with the participation of many economic sectors, export lacquer goods also suffered the same situation as other handicraft products, all fell into crisis. From 1993 onwards, cooperative models of production gradually disintegrated, replaced by private forms of production. Private establishments and companies with unfair competition, deliberately shorten production processes, reduce materials, use poor quality materials, paint plastics that do not meet the permissible standards, even replace them with industrial paints, Thai varnish, Taiwanese or cashew paint etc. The quality of wood for core work is also not good. At all levels and related sectors, there is a lack of synchronous combination, leading to many troublesome procedures such as if you want to have good wood to make the core, you must have the

seal of the forest ranger, you must pay environmental tax, and you must prove the origin. Then shipping procedures plus high prices. Then there's the cliché on the subject of templates etc and so on.

Current paint products (lacquer, optical paint, mosaic paint ...) including fine lacquer paintings fall into the situation of following traditional techniques, not coming to the place and escaping from tradition, revealing weaknesses both technically and aesthetically. Fine art paintings, jars, screens, mussel mosaics, lacquer paintings, plasters, boxes, bowls, plates ... Technically, it is sketchy, shortens the process, cuts the material, the aesthetics are rough, the lines and patterns lack sophistication, distillation, the colors are many but flashy, lack of sophistication, sometimes even smeared quite arbitrarily. The product design is monotonous, even eaten by foreigners. There is really a shortage of artists who are dedicated to creating and designing designs like before.

Through the recent ASEAN handicraft exhibition in Hanoi, we clearly see the need to think about Vietnamese lacquer handicrafts compared to those of Myanmar, Thailand, Indonesia, their paintwork far ahead of us in aesthetics and quality! Do we find the "downturn" from before alarming?

Another situation that public opinion is pressing is the construction and embellishment of historical and cultural relics, pavilions, pagodas, temples, shrines ... In fact, thanks to that work, the profession of decorating paints, statues, thrones, hammock doors, floats and other worship items is restored to develop, promote the national artistic identity, respect the people's freedom of belief. There are many valuable works and relics invested by the State at the right time and in the right place that have been seriously and skillfully reproduced by skillful and talented artisans and craftsmen in a serious, elaborate way, loyal to the inherent values from the past. These are works with state investment, with close technical and artistic direction, but the above works are not many.

Throughout the country, in addition to relics such as palaces and mausoleums of national character, there are many houses, pagodas, temples and shrines of cultural, historical and religious value. Among them, there are also many relics that have been ranked by the State, which are in need of restoration and upgrading. Due to the limited capital and budget of the State, the investment and direction are not much, most of the construction and repair are mainly contributed by the people, so the renovation, embellishment or construction of relics is strong, there is no one to direct and guide the technique and fine arts. Therefore, many of the completed renovations deteriorate, not worthy of a place of worship or not compatible with the overall architecture. There are many houses and temples where people contribute money to build new, not according to any architectural standards, the decoration and painting are also arbitrary, they hire their own painters, paint statues, decorate worship items ... The people hired to do these sanctuary works are mostly young people who are new to the profession, including famous places for long-standing traditional painting such as Son Dong, Vo Lang (Hanoi), they follow the so-called "market mechanism", cheap, cheap, expensive is expensive, in terms of stages, techniques, art is also in the way of "what money". For projects with little money, they use low-cost and convenient materials such as Japanese paint, gold, Japanese silver or tin, even using industrial emulsion paints, coated with glossy oil. The level of the owners of the project is very immature, even with mediocre and skewed artistic tastes. They have no knowledge of the technique of painting, painting statues, painting gold lipstick ... according to the traditional method, you should say why listen to it, as long as it is cheap (in fact, Japanese paint, Japanese colors have their own values, but when used without knowing how to be poor, it will cause objections, damage the building and cultural environment). Using imported materials is self-harming to domestic culture and economy).

Many overseas Viet Kieu or wealthy people in cities also often merit money to build houses and pagodas for their homeland. This funding is very important, but the construction, decoration, and painting must be done at the discretion of those who spend money, they say, what they want must be at their disposal. If you are a

qualified person, it is good, and if you do not encounter someone who depends on us, it will "give birth" to flamboyant, hybrid, patchwork works to the size and offensive.

As we all know, thanks to the traditional painting profession that has developed with good artisans and craftsmen plus precious and quality materials such as Phu Tho paint, we have a lot of beautiful painted interior decoration works, in palaces, temples, pagodas, mausoleums, the worshippers, the beautiful lacquer paintings, have endured through the centuries. Unfortunately, to this day, due to the lack of direction and guidance because it does not follow the process and methodical of traditional painting and paint, it has produced quite a lot of works that lack aesthetics and even ruined the achievements of our fathers.

The above thorny issues have also been disagreed by the public, but it seems that there is no solution to prevent the terrifying destruction of a new trend, damage and gradually destroy the technical and artistic values left by ancient times.

An alarming situation is that the number of artisans and skilled craftsmen of traditional paintwork and traditional lacquer art is increasingly absent. Many people have moved to other fields to make a living because in fact, production, creativity according to traditional painting methods and techniques, the profit is not high, only when there is an order, they will follow the process, traditional techniques, then return to the song "lower the price", reduce the process or even make it of other cheap and exotic materials.

Many private lacquer facilities also have explorations and disassembly. They combined lacquer with ceramics (mostly "new style" lacquers) which also had a positive economic effect. Many places to replace the physique with composite materials also have good effects, both cheap and easy to craft at will, can make physiques to draw large sizes, can make cores for statues, trays, boxes, jars, bowls, plates ... very favorable but in terms of durability and resistance to time, the harsh climate has not been tested.

The current situation of traditional craft villages being lost, shrunk or converted to other production and business sectors is alarming. For example, the very famous craft village Tuong Binh Hiep in Thu Dau Mot (with large establishments such as Thanh Le, Tran Ha) previously had over 500 households living by lacquer handicraft, but up to now only a few hundred households produce "crop pillows".

The traditional craft villages in the North, the cradle of our paint, traditional lacquer also share the same fate. Many craft villages have switched to making votive goods, making imitations, counterfeit goods such as cigarettes, soap, toothpaste, etc.

At art galleries, besides the establishments selling quality lacquer paintings, gallery owners know how to coordinate with artists to introduce and promote works, lacquer authors, create art spaces (this number is not many), there are many shops selling lacquer paintings that are poor in aesthetic value, looks very "fake", many imitations of "genuine" paintings selling well on the market are copyright violations.

However, it must be affirmed that in our country, lacquer art had a golden age, along with the brilliant development of lacquer materials in painting, lacquer materials and art also flourished in the fields of applied painting, handicrafts. Many interior decoration works for Party and State agencies, cultural and artistic works are also constructed, expressed through lacquer materials, lacquer paintings purchased and hung at offices, community activities... Shaping lacquer paintings and fine lacquer paintings help beautify the project. A series of researching, composing and producing handicrafts and lacquer paintings of the Ministry of Culture, the Ministry of Foreign Trade and the Central Socialist Union have contributed to promoting the development of Vietnamese lacquer art. A series of cooperatives, fine art workshops, lacquer production groups were also established and actively operated to serve the people's national livelihood, the aesthetic needs of the people and

especially for export. Lacquer paintings, works on lacquer handicraft products such as screens, flowerpots, boxes, trays, plates, decorative paintings, jewelry, etc. have come to the market of many countries very welcomed and admired. During the participation in international fairs and exhibitions, many lacquer works and products of Vietnam have also won worthy awards. Lacquer material (authentic) has brought "Title" to Vietnam while also bringing many economic benefits and creating jobs for millions of people.

It can be said that Vietnamese lacquer painting has made a proud development in materials and art. Lacquer in painting along with the achievements of lacquer in the field of decoration and handicrafts have created an ensemble, vivid in the fine arts of Vietnam.

4. Solutions to restore, revive and develop traditional Vietnamese lacquer paintings

Studying the situation and development of lacquer paintings - National Painting of Vietnam, we are proud of the creativity of our predecessors and see the responsibility of the next generation to preserve and promote cultural heritage. We need to focus on the following issues:

Preserving and promoting traditional materials

Through the test of time, the works shown, constructed with traditional materials, painting techniques, authentic lacquer, this material has proved its enduring value that is difficult to match. Phu Tho paint both creates a great artistic identity and protects the core and physique for a long time. A lot of painted works such as paintings, thrones, floats, hammock doors, diaphragms, couplets, worship objects. And other fine arts have existed for centuries, despite the harsh climatic and weather conditions in this tropical country. Due to soil and climatic conditions, the paint variety in the midlands of Phu Tho has given us the best paint resin in the world.

In recent years, establishments have rushed to use Polisai paint, cashew paint, Nam Vang paint, wagon varnish ... so the area planted with paintbrush is shrinking, converting crops. When the traditional paint and lacquer craft are revived and developed, the amount of paint Phu Tho has to use will increase many times. This plan also has to be taken care of early because planting paint trees cannot "overnight" but can harvest paint resin.

In addition to taking care of the main and most important material is paint plastic, there is also a need for scientific research to discover new materials used for traditional lacquer.

The state should have a planning area for the planting of paint. Especially Phu Tho paint tree, Phu Tho paint tree has long been a very good paint and has provided paint materials for craft villages with traditional lacquer craft.

Having a satisfactory policy with the cultivation of paint, paint growers can live by their profession. In this way, the cultivation of paint trees will develop again as before. Currently, artists and painters want to buy a good paint to paint is very difficult, it is also very expensive to buy. In fact, once the craft village has shrunk, the paint produced has no place to consume. Therefore, the paint growing area in Phu Tho has been gradually reduced to good paint varieties, instead of white paint varieties with high yield for a lot of latex, this paint is often exported to the Chinese market. An irony is that after Chinese enterprises buy it, they process it into ripe paint and return to Vietnam to sell it to the same country that grows it. Painters and painters have to buy and use, there is no other way for painters and artisans to use a paint that is inferior to many purple paints that have been had and grown a lot before. It is also because of the immediate economic benefits that paint growers have abandoned that precious paint variety.

In order to regain the traditional Vietnamese lacquer brand, preserving and preserving lacquer painting not only relies on the State, but also socializes, must be enterprises that know how to exploit this precious paint

cultivation. In this way, it is fortunate to restore the cultivation of paint, to develop it, there must be appropriate policies. Combining afforestation with raw material exploitation, promoting poverty alleviation, ensuring social security. and bring the development of craft villages, including lacquer painting.

It is not recently that Chinese people are interested in the techniques and materials of Vietnamese lacquer, but since the 50s and 60s of the twentieth century they have sent experts to learn and learn about Vietnamese lacquer. In recent years, lacquer and lacquer painting techniques in all localities of China have developed very aggressively and with high efficiency. Japanese people also pay a lot of attention to Vietnamese lacquer, typically the Japanese artist Saeko - Ando is very passionate and "selfless" with Vietnamese lacquer materials. The "Painted Tree" gallery on Nghi Tam Street (Hanoi) has attracted many foreign students to study and study authentic lacquer. Saeko confided, "... I have traveled to many countries but have no predestination, as my family said: "Saeko was probably Vietnamese in her previous life... Most Vietnamese artists paint lacquer because it is easy to sell or because it is a specialty of Vietnam, but not many people are skilled in lacquer. Good people with experience in lacquer often do not know foreign languages. Another problem, Vietnam has not yet had conditions for in-depth scientific research on lacquer, such as on paint...".

Some Japanese people come to Vietnam to go directly to the "Painted Tree" Gallery to learn, to draw. A Japanese NGO is cooperating with Saeko in upgrading Vietnamese lacquer technology to export to Japan.

There is no doubt that if we do not invest in development, this extremely valuable industry and material will disappear into a great sin for the National Ancestors. What will our children and grandchildren think in the future when they have to plow this apprenticeship in other countries! When there is something in hand, even if it is a treasure, people often look down on it, but when suddenly that treasure is lost, they regret it.

Policy regime for artisans and skilled craftsmen

In lacquer craft, artisans, painters, cores, physiques are very important. Currently, this profession has shown signs of disappearing, partly because the artisans in the craft village are old and have died most of them, the number of people passed down by their families is not much, most of them have converted to other professions with good income. The remaining few who want to retain the family tradition are also in a state of shaking, due to the increasing price of materials, not enough production costs. In short, the above reasons lead to the risk of obliterating the traditional lacquer making that generations of artisans have created.

The production of kneeling silver, kneeling gold, lipstick and other materials, the main tool materials of lacquer painting (such as mo tools, steel ...) are also in a difficult situation due to expensive materials, low workers' salaries, high life demand, etc. Therefore, to maintain large-scale production as before is gradually reduced. Lipstick materials are the same, there is only 1 artisan now I have passed the craft to my children but the lipstick is not of satisfactory quality (I do not want to sell the recipe), some people try to make lipstick but not as if ... (A good news is that in Kieu Kieu - Gia Lam - Hanoi, where there is a traditional profession of making kneeling gold, kneeling silver, there have been people investing to revive the profession - This information has been communicated by radio).

In many countries, especially China and Japan, artisans and skilled craftsmen are very favored, appreciated and patronized. For artisans who represent unique and unique traditional professions, they are paid very high salaries by the State. This grant can open research, composition and testing workshops to develop and improve the quality of the profession, can open vocational training for students who are dedicated to the profession with a "respect for the religion". Typical artisans are always honored as "Living Cultural Assets of the nation, of the nation" and they deserve the same.

In Vietnam in the past, talented artisans were also respected, being awarded the title of "nine products" exempt from the epidemic. In the French colonial period, the famous artisan Dinh Van Thanh was very skilled, skilled in traditional painting, was invited to teach at the Indochina College of Fine Arts. Artist Dinh Van Thanh was sent to Paris (France) to attend the exhibition, bringing tools and tools to "perform", manipulating the techniques of Vietnamese paint and lacquer. From the day peace was restored (after 1954) artisan Dinh Van Thanh was again invited to teach vocational training at the School of Fine Arts (now the University of Industrial Fine Arts). Talking about artist Dinh Van Thanh, artist Le Quoc Loc commented and evaluated: "... Uncle Dinh Van Thanh is a person who loves to explore and improve. Throughout his life, he always paid attention to improving his workmanship, how to process paint so well. I often talk about professional conscience, I think that if you have a conscience that loves the profession, technology will advance. And the dishonest person who likes to fake to make money is a sham ... Uncle Dinh Van Thanh honestly deserves the title of True Artisan. Through the fine arts you show, each deserves to be called a work. It goes beyond what's called normal craftsmanship. Looking at each product created by him, seeing the elaborate labor, carefully from the core, from paint to shaping, shaping and decorating., that is the standard for domestic or export lacquer art to follow. How to make lacquer handicrafts as well as in the lacquer field of visual arts ... Artist Dinh Van Thanh always thinks about the profession, is always creative and has been admitted to the Vietnam Fine Arts Association since the early 60s of the last century ...".

During the subsidy period, the authorities were also very interested in, helping and honoring artisans. The Central Commune Union, the Fine Arts Department of the Ministry of Culture, and the Vietnam Fine Arts Association also regularly encourage and create conditions for artisans to devote themselves to their careers. Many artisans have been sent abroad to participate in exhibitions to have conditions to exchange, learn skills and art of other countries. Many artisans have been selected and honored with the "Golden Hand Artisan".

Currently, in the market, the team of traditional paint artisans, authentic lacquer is increasingly absent, they are not as respected as before. Conditions for working in a genuine profession were affected because the income was not enough to support themselves, so most of them switched to other professions, with more stable incomes. Traditional paint materials, traditional lacquer are not promoted. There is no authority to take care of these "Living Cultural Properties". Where to find artisans who are dedicated to the profession, have depth, experience, talent, and skillful skills like Uncle Thanh, Uncle Number, Uncle Doan in the past. At this momentum, with the penetration of foreign materials, gradually the risk of losing the "Ancestral Craft" is possible.

People are the most precious capital, artisans and skilled workers are the most important of the traditional profession. If there is no regime, policy, worthy patronage and specific strategy for skilled artisans and craftsmen, a few decades from now, if you can realize it, it will be too late, if you try to salvage it, there will not be much left.

Good, talented artisans are usually at the age of "Rare". They can't "wait" for another few decades!

The role of State Management

This factor is decisive. Only the State with ministries, departments and functional branches has the potential and power to clear the current impasse and deviance. Without the direction, organization, in-depth investment, sponsorship, research, composition and consumption of works and products, the "floating" situation will still exist and develop.

The "golden" period of traditional lacquer craftsmanship, authentic lacquer handicrafts flourished during the subsidy period. Of course we cannot go back to the patterns and methods of subsidy times; In the market

mechanism, in the trend of international exchange and integration, if we want to preserve and develop this unique and unique traditional industry, we need a long-term strategy. The state must become a generous and practical "midwife". Only the State with ministries, departments and functional branches can highlight the work of directing the organization of a synchronous system of training, production and output for lacquer painting and traditional lacquer handicrafts. Only the State can organize competitions and exhibitions to mobilize forces and have policies for good artists, artisans and craftsmen. Only the State can establish a number of organizations (such as corporations) to have a complete apparatus to take care of the following areas: training, scientific research, composition and experimentation of new designs, new techniques, product introduction, signing contracts for the consumption of works, products with countries around the world. In the short term, we may suffer losses and losses, but in the long run, we will get big things to restore and revive a profession with a unique Vietnamese national identity, while encouraging and restoring craft villages and creating jobs for millions of workers who have had "golden hands" since ancient times.

The socialization policy of the Party and the State, the freedom to develop industries create favorable conditions but it is necessary to have appropriate and oriented policies to avoid the situation of "floating", unfair competition of the market (there are problems that need subsidies that still have to be invested by the State).

5. CONCLUSIONS

Vietnamese lacquer paintings have a history of nearly a century. With the unique beauty hidden talents, souls and creativity of Vietnamese people, it has created the unique value of Culture, contributing to bringing Vietnamese fine arts to a position in regional and world fine arts.

Studying Vietnamese lacquer paintings in the current situation and development shows us the history of Vietnamese paint culture in similarities and differences with neighboring countries and continents to see the mutual influence, see the cultural quintessence passed down from generation to generation to create cultural identity. In the process of movement and development, there have been innovations and creations that make bright lipstick, one of the bright spots is Vietnam Lacquer Painting.

The technique and art of traditional lacquer also hides its magical and limitless potential. We don't have to get to the bottom of discovery and creativity. The mission of acquiring and developing this "treasure" is on the shoulders of today's generations. The brilliant achievements, typical works of lacquer art have proved and affirmed the great expressive ability for all subjects and all art styles. The shiny, deep but splendid with durability despite all weather, climate, environment and time conditions ... ask who doesn't admire! The traditional painting village where cultural features and cultural heritages about people are preserved in terms of occupation is very respectable. Preserving and honoring traditional lacquer craft villages also contributes to the development of economic culture and tourism.

In order to restore, revive and develop traditional paintwork, lacquer art, lacquer painting, issues such as the source of raw materials, materials / Vocational training / Policy regime for artisans, skilled workers / Scientific and technological research / State management ... very relevant to help the conservation and development of Vietnamese lacquer paintings.

The great achievements, skills, creativity in materials and lacquer art are due to the many enthusiasm and talents of the previous people who have openly explored, explored, summarized ... that yes. For example, one day, due to our indifference and irresponsibility, this achievement, this precious capital will be "handed out" to other countries that they really know how to invest appropriately, fully exploit, turn into their great strengths and interests? At that time, surely, the owners of this extremely precious heritage will have to be extremely sorry.

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